

Supporting information

Probing Interfacial Interactions: Ionic Liquids and Cellulose Thin Films

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Calculation of ion pair volumes

The method was adapted from Slattery et al. (2007) but here in brief how it works: It is not necessary to know the precise crystal structure of the liquid under investigation and we can use the following approach: We can determine the sizes of certain ions by looking at crystals containing similar ions of known sizes. These known sizes can be accessed via databases, e.g. the CCDC database. For instance, we can look at the crystal size of sodium formate (SF) (Allan et al., 1999) ($V_{SF}=229.53 \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z=4$, $Z'=1$). By knowing the size of the sodium cation (Jenkins et al., 1999) ($V_{Na^+}=3.94 \text{ \AA}^3$) we can now get the information about the formate anion $[\text{OFm}]^-$. Be aware of Z , which refers to the number of sodium formate molecules in one crystal lattice. Therefore 229.53 \AA^3 (V_{SF}) needs to be divided by 4 (Z) and then simply subtracted by 3.94 \AA^3 (V_{Na^+}) (**eq S1**).

$$V_{\text{OFm}^-} = \frac{V_{SF}}{Z} - V_{Na^+} \quad \text{eq S1}$$

This leads to the size of 53.44 \AA^3 $[\text{OFm}]^-$ anion. By doing this for multiple known crystal lattices, the end result gets more precise e.g., using additionally ammonium formate. Even if we lack the structure of a crystal with a specific ion, we can estimate its size by looking at similar ions in a series. By comparing different alkyl chain lengths, for instance, we can make an educated guess about the ion's size. This estimation is quicker and simpler than determining the crystal structure. However, we need to be cautious about where we start this estimation in the series. The calculated and used ion pair volumes of the ionic liquids in this study are stated in table S1 (**Table S1**).

Table S1 Determination of crystal volumes of the investigated ionic liquids.

Ionic liquids	$V_{ion\ pair}/\text{\AA}^3$	$V_{cation}/\text{\AA}^3$	$V_{anion}/\text{\AA}^3$	References
[BMIM][ACR]	287.57	196	91.57	(Oswald et al., 2011; Slattery et al., 2007)
[BMIM][OAc]	268.36	196	72.36	(Dawson et al., 2004; Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][ACR]	247.57	156	91.57	(Oswald et al., 2011; Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][DCA]	245.00	156	89	(Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][DEP]	359.41	156	203.41	(Ezra et al., 1973; Jenkins et al., 1999; Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][OAc]	228.36	156	72.36	(Dawson et al., 2004; Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][OOC]	377.15	156	221.15	(Bond, 2004; Slattery et al., 2007)
[EMIM][OPr]	256.66	156	100.66	(Slattery et al., 2007; Strieter et al., 1962)
[EMIM][TFSI]	388.00	156	232	(Nockemann et al., 2009; Slattery et al., 2007)
[HEXMIM][ACR]	333.57	242	91.57	(Oswald et al., 2011; Slattery et al., 2007)

Table S2: Ionic liquid molecular weight, structure and radius of the ion pair.

Ionic liquid	Molecular weight/g·mol ⁻¹	Molecular formular	-Structure	Radius (r_{cation}) of the cation ^a /Å	Radius (r_{anion}) of the anion ^a /Å
[BMIM][ACR]	210.28	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂		3.60	2.80
[BMIM][OAc]	198.26	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂		3.60	2.59
[EMIM][ACR]	182.23	C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂		3.34	2.80
[EMIM][DCA]	177.21	C ₈ H ₁₁ N ₅		3.34	2.77
[EMIM][DEP]	264.26	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ P		3.34	3.65
[EMIM][OAc]	170.21	C ₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂		3.34	2.59
[EMIM][OOC]	254.37	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂		3.34	3.75
[EMIM][OPr]	184.24	C ₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂		3.34	2.89
[EMIM][TFSI]	391.31	C ₈ H ₁₁ F ₆ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂		3.34	3.81
[HEXMIM][ACR]	238.34	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂		3.87	2.80

^acalculated when assuming anion and cation resemble together a sphere with $V_{ion} = \frac{3}{4} \cdot r_{ion}^3 \cdot \pi$

Water content

Figure S1: Water content in wt.-% of the ionic liquids used in this study. Reprinted with permission under the open access license CC-BY 4.0. (Pachernegg et al., 2024)

Cellulose thin films

To further investigate the cellulose thin film, reference measurements of water, diiodomethane, ethylene glycol and glycerin (**Figure S2, left**) have been performed. The static contact angles were compared to literature values and the measured values are within the literature deviations. Depending on the experimental execution of the cellulose thin film production, the values for the static contact angle vary significantly (**Figure S2**). Especially the use of the solvent has a drastic influence on the derived thin film. (Kargl et al., 2015; Mohan et al., 2011; Niegelhell et al., 2018; Sampl et al., 2021; Schaubeder et al., 2022) The higher boiling point of toluene, which was used by Kargl et al. (2015) and Mohan et al. (2011) leads therefore to a difference in surface structure and ultimately to a difference in the measured contact angle (**Figure S2, left**).

Figure S2: **(Left)**: Contact angle of cellulose thin films in literature. Films by Mohan et al. were prepared from TMSC in toluene.(Mohan et al., 2011) Films by Kargl et al. were prepared out of an ionic liquid solution.(Kargl et al., 2015) Films prepared by Sampl et al. (2021), Schaubeder et al. (2022), and Niegelhell et al. (2018) were prepared via spin coating of a TMSC solution in chloroform. **(Right)**: ATR-IR spectrum of the regenerated cellulose thin film with the significant C-Si bands in yellow.

The broad band between 3600 and 3000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the OH-stretch of cellulose (and residual water) (**Figure S2, right**).(Kontturi et al., 2003; Mohan et al., 2012). Further typical bands for cellulose include the CH-stretching at 2900 cm^{-1} , the OH bending of adsorbed water at 1635 cm^{-1} and the HCH and OCH in-plane bending vibrations at 1430 cm^{-1} .(Oh et al., 2005) The Si-C contributions, which stem from the TMSC, present as symmetrically Si-C deformation vibrations at 1251 cm^{-1} and additional vibrations in the range of 875-750 cm^{-1} respectively, are not present in the regenerated film (**Figure S2, right, green line**) (Bontea, 2002; Kontturi et al., 2003; Kostag et al., 2010), which confirms the full regeneration of the films after HCl treatment.

Figure S3: AFM phase images of (A) the TMSC thin film and (B) the regenerated cellulose thin film.

Fitting procedure MKT

For error determination the R^2 -error is calculated according to (eq S2):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2} \quad \text{eq S2}$$

Where y_i is the calculated value, \hat{y}_i is the experimental value and \bar{y}_i is the mean of the experimental values.

Figure S4: Schematic illustration of the calculation of the minimal R^2 -error.

MKT Literature review

Table S3 Literature data on jump calculated MKT values. Selected literature references using (i) ionic liquids or (ii) similar surfaces for comparison.

Liquid	Surface	Jump frequency k_w^0 /MHz	Jump length $\lambda/\text{\AA}$	Ref.
[HMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Glass	1.08 ± 0.16	8.8 ± 0.4	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[OMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Glass	0.34 ± 0.11	11.2 ± 0.7	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[DDMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Glass	0.44 ± 0.05	9.1 ± 0.2	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[HMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Gold	0.71 ± 0.06	8.8 ± 0.2	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[OMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Gold	0.54 ± 0.08	10.2 ± 0.4	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[DDMIM][NTf ₂] ^a	Gold	0.31 ± 0.3	9.4 ± 0.2	(Delcheva et al., 2018)
[EMIM][BF ₄]	Teflon AF1600	7.2	9.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[BMIM][BF ₄]	Teflon AF1600	3.5	9.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[OMIM][BF ₄]	Teflon AF1600	1.0	9.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[EMIM][NTf ₂]	Teflon AF1600	12.8	8.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[BMIM][NTf ₂]	Teflon AF1600	10.0	8.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[HMIM][NTf ₂]	Teflon AF1600	4.8	8.0	(Li et al., 2011)
[EMIM][BF ₄]	Polydimethylsiloxane	3.93 ± 0.28	6.8 ± 0.1	(Aldhaleai et al., 2022)
[HMIM][NTf ₂]	Polydimethylsiloxane	1.73 ± 0.16	7.9 ± 0.2	(Aldhaleai et al., 2022)
[BMIM][BF ₄]	Polydimethylsiloxane	0.84 ± 0.05	6.7 ± 0.2	(Aldhaleai et al., 2022)
Water	PET	8600	3.6	(Berg, 1993)
16% glycerol/water	PET	3600	4.6	(Berg, 1993)
86% glycerol/water	PET	35	4.6	(Berg, 1993)

Di- <i>n</i> -butyl phthalate	PET	0.11	18.0	(Berg, 1993)
Silicone oil ^b ($\eta^c = 0.958 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)	Glass	0.23	8.0	(Hoffman, 1975)
Silicone oil ^b ($\eta^c = 98.8 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)	Glass	0.0023	8.0	(Hoffman, 1975)
Water	Glass	20.24 ± 4.50	6.2 ± 0.06	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
20 wt.% glycerol/water	Glass	11.70 ± 1.20	6.2 ± 0.06	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
40 wt.% glycerol/water	Glass	6.88 ± 0.30	6.2 ± 0.06	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
60 wt.% glycerol/water	Glass	5.42 ± 0.24	6.2 ± 0.06	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
80 wt.% glycerol/water	Glass	1.22 ± 0.04	5.99 ± 0.05	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
90 wt.% glycerol/water	Glass	0.354 ± 0.013	6.41 ± 0.04	(Duvivier et al., 2011)
Water	PET	1.6	7.2	(Hayes et al., 1994)
Glycerol/water	PET	0.0011	19	(Hayes et al., 1994)

^ameasured with Wilhelmy plate method, ^bmeasured with a meniscus apparatus, ^cdynamic viscosity

Physical properties of ionic liquids

Table S4 Physical data of ionic liquids, used for the modeling Data from Pachernegg et al. (Pachernegg et al., 2024)

	Surface tension/ $\text{mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$	Density/ $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$	Viscosity/ $\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$	Reference
BMIM-ACR	35.52	1.061	313.780	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)

BMIM-OAC	37.54	1.057	344.597	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-TFSI	35.98	1.523	29.785	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-ACR	45.27	1.110	93.000	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-DCA	57.7	1.102	14.850	(Safarov et al., 2021)
EMIM-DEP	35.35	1.147	277.546	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-OAC	48.37	1.101	117.973	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-OOC	31.09	0.998	472.000	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
EMIM-OPr	40.74	1.078	131.830	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)
HEXMIM-ACR	31.25	1.030	517.467	(Pachernegg et al., 2024)

Hydrodynamic model

Viscous dissipation in the liquid phase is the dominant factor in the hydrodynamic model. (Cox, 1986; Voinov, 1977) The classic hydrodynamic method fails to describe the flow behavior close to the three-phase contact line. The failure is ascribed to the incompatibility between the motion dictated by the contact line and the no-slip boundary condition at the solid–liquid interface which would (mathematically) lead to an infinite stress of the liquid towards the surface. (Huh et al., 1971) In order to avoid such singularity due to enforcing the no-slip condition, a slip condition is often introduced

near the contact line. (Dussan, 1979; Hansen et al., 1971; Huh et al., 1971) The formulated model (Cox, 1986) (eq S3) represents a relation between the contact line velocity, v [$m \cdot s^{-2}$], and the dynamic contact angle θ_d and the static contact angle calculated by the hydrodynamic model θ_{HD} in [$^\circ$]:

$$g(\theta_d) = g(\theta_{HD}) \pm \frac{\eta v}{\gamma_{LV}} \ln \frac{L}{L_s} \quad \text{eq S3}$$

The positive sign is for advancing contact lines, while the minus sign is for receding contact lines. Here L is a characteristic macroscopic length scale [m] e.g., the diameter of the droplet and L_s is a microscopic slip length [m], which should be in the order of the molecules. Primary in this model is viscous friction, whereby the resultant viscous force F_v [N] is given by (eq S4)

$$F_v = \mu v = 3\eta \frac{\theta_d}{\ln \frac{L}{L_s}} v \quad \text{eq S4}$$

where $\mu = 3\eta \ln(L/L_s)/\theta_d$ is the friction coefficient within the bulk. (Brochard-Wyart et al., 1992) For liquid-vapor systems with $\theta < 150^\circ$, the function $g(\theta_d)$ simplifies to $\approx \theta_d^3/9$ within 1% accuracy and the so-called Voinov equation (Petrov et al., 2003; Schneemilch et al., 1998) can be formulated:

$$\theta_d^3 = \theta_{HD}^3 + 9 \frac{\eta v}{\gamma_{LV}} \ln \frac{L}{L_s} \quad \text{eq S5}$$

Free variables in the equation S5 (eq S5), are the static contact angle (θ_{HD}) and the logarithmic length scale ratio $\ln(L/L_s)$ which provide parameters for modeling dynamic wetting behavior. We used equation S5 (eq S5) for our calculations.

Table S5 Calculated values for the fitting coefficients and of the HD-model when separating between fast and low spreading speeds.

	Fast spreading ($>0.000125 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)			Slow spreading ($<0.000125 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)		
	R^2	$\ln\left(\frac{L}{L_s}\right)$	$\theta_{HD}/^\circ$	R^2	$\ln\left(\frac{L}{L_s}\right)$	$\theta_{HD}/^\circ$
[BMIM][ACR]	0.74	$4.40 \cdot 10^6$	28.66	0.64	$5.23 \cdot 10^6$	27.43
[BMIM][OAc]	0.26	$4.14 \cdot 10^6$	10.90	0.10	$1.79 \cdot 10^6$	28.87
[EMIM][TFSI]	0.26	$2.41 \cdot 10^7$	36.93	0.12	$2.30 \cdot 10^7$	33.66
[EMIM][ACR]	0.80	$3.27 \cdot 10^7$	34.38	0.66	$4.38 \cdot 10^7$	30.76
[EMIM][DCA]	0.55	$2.78 \cdot 10^7$	17.52	0.03	$1.01 \cdot 10^7$	21.51
[EMIM][DEP]	0.36	$2.97 \cdot 10^6$	9.17	0.10	$1.29 \cdot 10^6$	26.35
[EMIM][OAc]	0.52	$1.11 \cdot 10^7$	29.72	0.10	$6.44 \cdot 10^6$	30.73

[EMIM][OOC]	0.31	$1.51 \cdot 10^6$	19.95	0.08	$7.82 \cdot 10^5$	26.17
[EMIM][OPr]	0.09	$2.05 \cdot 10^6$	31.40	0.06	$3.26 \cdot 10^6$	28.28
[HEXMIM][ACR]	0.44	$9.21 \cdot 10^5$	6.78	0.04	$2.51 \cdot 10^5$	22.53

Usually the spreading is separated into two distinct regions: (i) a fast initial spreading and a (ii) second slower spreading region. (Li et al., 2011) In the case of this experimental data, we separated the two regions at $0.000125 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. By fitting equation S5 (**eq S5**) to the experimental we obtain the values for static contact angle θ_{HD} and the logarithmic length scale ratio $\ln(L/L_s)$ (**Table S4**). Even though the fit in the initial fast spreading region provides reasonable values for θ_{HD} , the values for the length scale ratio are not physically viable. This supports the hypothesis by Li et al. (Li et al., 2011) on obtaining non-reasonable values of the HD model to describe ionic liquid drop spreading.

Calculated Molecular-kinetic data

Table S6 Jump frequency and length calculated with equation 7 (**eq 7**), without constraints.

Ionic liquid	Jump frequency	Standard deviation	Jump length	Standard deviation
		jump frequency		jump length
	κ_s^0		λ	
	GHz	GHz	Å	Å
[BMIM][ACR]	11.29	2.05	10.16	0.27
[BMIM][OAc]	18.20	3.21	8.40	1.01
[EMIM][TFSI]	0.25	0.15	14.29	1.88
[EMIM][ACR]	2.61	0.40	8.28	0.31
[EMIM][DCA]	2.60	0.79	7.61	0.39
[EMIM][DEP]	13.95	4.08	10.71	0.72
[EMIM][OAc]	3.49	1.25	8.91	0.64
[EMIM][OOC]	12.01	6.25	12.69	1.18
[EMIM][OPr]	5.72	0.89	8.86	0.40
[HEXMIM][ACR]	16.17	4.54	12.80	0.40

Results of the fitting procedure (MKT)

As one can see in Fig. S4 to Fig. S13, below a contact angle of 40°, the velocity shows some significant jumps. These jumps are attributed to the fitting procedure of the SCA20 software, and represents regions where the fitting algorithm, does not adequately determine the drop boundaries (areas of low contrast between wafer surface and drop). These errors are filtered upon fitting as outliers and do not interfere with the calculation.

Figure S5 Average R²-values of [BMIM][ACR] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S6 Average R²-values of [BMIM][OAc] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S7 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][TFSI] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S8 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][ACR] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S9 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][DCA] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S10 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][DEP] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S11 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][OAc] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S12 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][OOc] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S13 Average R^2 -values of [EMIM][OPr] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

Figure S14 Average R^2 -values of [HEXMIM][ACR] and the spreading velocity vs the contact angle evolvement of the same liquid.

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